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Validation of a knowledge-based planning model: statistics versus clinical experiences

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Introduction: Using knowledge-based planning (KBP) is a solution for clinics that have a shortage of staff, in our situation a shortage of medical physicists, even though they are medical physics degree program in the country. The KBP planning is also faster planning solution in clinics that have a large number of patients. The aim of the work was to validate the KBP model from the existing database of gynecological treatment plans using clinical experiences since the statistical parameters of the model were not met.

Material and Methods: The KBP model was designed with 89 gynecological treatment plans from one institution database. The model parameters included PTV as target structure and bladder, rectum, bowel bag, anal canal, and femoral heads as organs at risk structures. Validation of the model included analysis of 22 patients, and they were compared with clinical plans. The quality of the model was quantified using clinical constraints, and the plans were also visual analyzed.

Results: According to the international guidelines and national protocol, all the parameters that were monitored were within the allowed limits, as shown in Table 1. The mean values of the observed constraints are smaller with the KBP model, as shown in Table 1. Significant differences in the volume of the structures and their mutual relation showed the expected results obtained by the model.

Conclusion: The results showed that clinically acceptable plans are obtained with the model, which indicates that the model can be used in clinical practice. Beside statistical results, clinical expertise have significant role in understanding quality of KBP model.

Keywords: knowledge-based radiotherapy planning, gynecological, validation

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